

Handling Unbalanced Data by Weighting a Gamma Distribution for Image Segmentation

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ABSTRACT:

Handling imbalanced data is important in optimizing image classification and segmentation, where some classes may be underrepresented relative to others. A common approach to managing this imbalance is class weighting, which assigns higher weights to minority classes to compensate for their underrepresentation. In this paper, we propose an efficient weighting method based on a probability distribution, such as the Gamma distribution. It is a flexible model that can adjust class weights based on their density and shape. By assigning a Gamma density to each class, pixels belonging to minority classes can be given more importance by adjusting the shape parameters α and the pixel density parameter β specific to the distribution. When applying Gamma weighting, each pixel in the image is adjusted according to its class's Gamma density. This makes learning more sensitive to underrepresented classes. Weighting can be applied both before and after image segmentation or transformation, providing flexibility to better manage the influence of classes on learning.

Keywords: unbalanced data, gamma distribution, image segmentation, loss function, artificial intelligence.

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INTRODUCTION

Handling imbalanced data is crucial in image classification and segmentation tasks. When certain classes are underrepresented, this can negatively impact model performance. Class weighting, particularly using distributions such as Gamma, helps compensate for this imbalance by adjusting the impact of minority classes [1,2]. This approach improves learning, ensuring better consideration of rare classes and optimizing results in imbalanced environments [3,4].

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METHODOLOGY

Handling imbalanced data using distribution weighting involves several key steps. First, the image is normalized to standardize intensities. Next, a Gamma probability density is applied to adjust pixel importance based on their class. Gamma weighting is then used to recalibrate pixels, followed by a Gamma transformation to modulate intensity. A final normalization adjusts the values, and finally, segmentation is performed to classify pixels, allowing for efficient management of minority classes.

Binarization and Normalization of the Image

To simplify data analysis during image segmentation, converting an image to grayscale is necessary. This step involves transforming a color image into a monochrome representation, eliminating color information while retaining variations in light intensity [5]. This is often achieved by calculating a weighted average of the red, green, and blue (RGB) channels [6]. Binarization, on the other hand, transforms a grayscale image into a binary image composed of only two values, usually black and white, by applying a threshold [7] [8]. Image I is finally normalized so that its pixel values fall within the interval $[0, 1]$. The formula is as follows:

$$\hat{I}(x, y) = \frac{I(x, y)}{255} \quad (1)$$

Where $I(x, y)$ is the pixel intensity at position (x, y) et $\hat{I}(x, y)$ is the normalized pixel value.

Gamma Distribution

In this step, the calculation of a weight w of the class c_i is introduced where c_i is the class that categorizes each object which can be the image itself or its background. This weight is calculated from the probability density of the Gamma distribution, which is adapted to the frequencies of the classes. Thus, let $p(c)$ be the a priori probability of a class c , and suppose that we have a Gamma distribution to model these probabilities. The weighting formula is as follows [9] [10] [11]:

$$w(c) = f(c) \cdot 1 / \sum_{i=1}^N f(c_i) \quad (2)$$

Where :

- $f(c)$ is the probability density of the c class according to the Gamma distribution.
- N is the total number of classes (in the case where the image and its background alone are considered then $N= 2$).
- $f(c_i)$ is the probability density for each class c_i of the Gamma distribution.

Probability density of Gamma

The Gamma probability density is used to weight the pixels. It is defined by [12] :

$$f(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} x^{\alpha-1} e^{-\beta x} \quad (3)$$

Where x , α and β are positive integers and $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt \quad (4)$$

And

- α is the shape parameter,
- β is the rate parameter,

Density $f\hat{I}(i, j); \alpha, \beta$ is applied to each pixel of the normalized image $\hat{I}(i, j)$

Role of α and β

α is the shape parameter that controls the curvature or shape of the distribution

- If $\alpha < 1$ then the distribution is strongly asymmetrical and thus concentrated towards 0.
- If $\alpha > 1$ then the distribution is symmetrical and spread around its mean.
- If $\alpha = 1$ then the distribution is exponential and we find a rapid decrease.

β is the scale parameter that influences the width or spread of the distribution

- If β is very large then the distribution becomes flatter and more widespread
- If β is very small then the distribution becomes more concentrated

Initialization of α and β

1. Data statistics-based approach

This approach is suitable for relative frequencies of known classes. So the average μ and variance σ^2 are parameters given in the hypothesis. Thus, the relations are given by:

$$\alpha = \frac{\mu^2}{\sigma^2} \quad (5)$$

And

$$\beta = \frac{\sigma^2}{\mu} \quad (6)$$

2. Approach based on empirical hypotheses

For segmentation tasks with rare classes, specific values of α and β are used.

- For $\alpha = 2$, the distribution is slightly asymmetrical
- For $\beta = 1$, the distribution is concentrated near the mean of the frequencies.

This approach works well if class frequencies have moderate disparities. If rare classes are extremely underrepresented, then increasing β (e.g. to 5) is highly recommended to have more weighting. Approche basée sur l'équilibrage des classes

Class proportions $freq_c$ are used to directly adjust α and β .

- The average frequency of the classes is then given by

$$\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{c=1}^N freq_c \quad (7)$$

Where N is the total number of classes.

- The value of β can be set to control the concentration around the mean.
- The value of α is adjusted to give the desired shape, whether asymmetric or balanced.

3. Approach based on metric optimization

α and β can be defined based on the maximization of the metric or the minimization of the loss that characterizes the evaluation function of the metric (F1-Score or chi-square). In general $\alpha \in [1, 5]$ and $\beta \in [0.5, 2]$

Managing Unbalanced Data

In image segmentation, unbalanced classes, which are rare regions, can be modeled using a gamma distribution to weight the importance of these classes. Common steps are:

a) Weighting based on the Gamma distribution

The parameters α and β can be used to assign adaptive weights based on the frequency of a class c in the data. A common formula for the weights is:

$$w_c = \frac{\beta^\alpha f(\text{freq}_c; \alpha, \beta)}{\sum_{c'} \beta^\alpha f(\text{freq}_{c'}; \alpha, \beta)} \quad (8)$$

Where freq_c is the normalized frequency of class c . This weighting favors rare classes by giving them a weight proportional to their density in a gamma distribution.

b) Weighted loss function

Using the weights w_c , the loss function for a segmentation can be modified. A weighted version of the cross-entropy loss is of the form:

$$L_{\text{pondérée}} = - \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C w_c y_{i,c} \log(\hat{y}_{i,c}) \quad (9)$$

Where :

- N is the number of pixels.
- C is the number of classes.
- $y_{i,c}$ is the ground truth for pixel i , which identifies the correct class for each pixel, if pixel i is in the background (c_1), we would have $y_{i,c_1}=1$ and $y_{i,c_2}=0$.
- $\hat{y}_{i,c}$ is the predicted probability for class c and from the softmax function of the neural network which transforms the logits into probability:

$$\hat{y}_{i,c} = e^{z_{i,c}} * 1 / \sum_{c' \in C} e^{z_{i,c'}} \quad (10)$$

Where i : Pixel index

c : Current class

C : All classes

$z_{i,c}$: Logit for pixel i and class c

and $z_{i,c} = W_c * x_i + b_c$

where

W_c : is a weight vector learned for the class c ,

x_i : is the vector of extracted features for pixel i

b_c : is the bias learned for class c

$W_c * x_i$: is a weighted sum of the elements of x_i

$e^{z_{i,c}}$: Exponential of logit

$\sum_{c' \in C} e^{z_{i,c'}}$: Sum of the exponentials of the logits

To avoid excessive overweighting of rare classes, we can introduce a regularization on the weights:

$$w_c = \frac{\beta^\alpha f(freq_c; \alpha, \beta) + \lambda}{\sum_{c' \in C} (\beta^\alpha f(freq_{c'}; \alpha, \beta) + \lambda)} \quad (11)$$

Where $\lambda > 0$ is a hyperparameter.

RESULTS

In this article, the PNG image of a lemur with dimensions 286 x 430 is used. The aim is to apply the details of the methodology on the management of unbalanced data with a gamma distribution applied to image segmentation. Thus, for this image we can define two classes: class c_1 which is the background image. It is thus formed by the entire transparent background because it is a png image. Class c_2 is formed by the bamboo and the lemur. The classes are unbalanced; the lemur and the bamboo occupy fewer pixels compared to its background [13].

Figure 1. Original Lemur Photo

a) Calculation of class frequencies

Let's assume that:

- The total number of pixels: N is equal to 10,000
- The distribution of pixels by class is then
 - Background (c_1) : 8000 pixels (80%).
 - Lemur (c_2) : 2000 pixels (20%).

The frequencies of the classes are then:

$$freq_{c_1} = \frac{8000}{10000} = 0.8 \quad freq_{c_2} = \frac{2000}{10000} = 0.2$$

b) Calculation of the Gamma distribution function

As the gamma distribution is defined by the two parameters α and β , we used the empirical approach to facilitate the analysis with consideration of unbalanced data.

- $\alpha = 2$ for the shape parameter
- $\beta = 5$ for the scale parameter

The formula for a given frequency is:

$$f(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} x^{\alpha-1} e^{-\beta x} \quad (12)$$

Where $\Gamma(\alpha)$ for $\alpha = 2$ is $\Gamma(2) = 1$

So

$$f(x; \alpha = 2, \beta = 5) = \frac{5^2}{\Gamma(2)} x^{2-1} e^{-5x}$$

c) Calculation of class densities

As we have two classes C_1 and C_2 and replacing the value of the frequency of the classes in the previous equation then :

1. *Image background*

We have $x = 0.8$:

$$f(0.8; 2, 5) = \frac{5^2}{\Gamma(2)} 0.8^1 e^{-5 \cdot 0.8} = 25 * 0.8 * e^{-4}$$

By taking $e^{-4} \approx 0.0183$ then $f(0.8; 2, 5) = 0.366$

2. *Lemur and bamboo object*

We have $x = 0.2$:

$$f(0.2; 2, 5) = \frac{5^2}{\Gamma(2)} 0.2^1 e^{-5 \cdot 0.2} = 25 * 0.2 * e^{-1}$$

By taking $e^{-1} \approx 0.3679$ then $f(0.2; 2, 5) = 1.839$

d) Weighting of classes

The equation (4) give us :

$$w_c = \frac{\beta^\alpha f(\text{freq}_c; \alpha, \beta)}{\sum_c (\beta^\alpha f(\text{freq}_c; \alpha, \beta))}$$

With the sum of the densities is $\sum_{c'} = f(0.8; 2, 5) + f(0.2; 2, 5) = 0.366 + 1.839 = 2.205$

1. *Image background c_1*

We have $f(0.8; 2, 5) = 0.366$:

$$w_{c_1} = \frac{f(0.8; 2, 5)}{\sum_{c'}} = \frac{0.366}{2.205} = 0.166$$

2. *Lemur and bamboo Object c_2*

We have $f(0.2; 2, 5) = 1.839$:

$$w_2 = \frac{f(0.2; 2, 5)}{\sum_{c'}} = \frac{1.839}{2.205} = 0.834$$

e) *Application in a loss function*

As a reminder, for a pixel i belonging to the ground truth y_i and the predicted probability $\hat{y}_{i,c}$, the weighted loss is:

$$L_{Pondérée} = - \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{c=1}^C w_c y_{i,c} \log(\hat{y}_{i,c}) \quad (13)$$

For a ground truth pixel c_2 , therefore belonging to the lemur, we have $y_{i,c_1} = 1$ et $y_{i,c_2} = 0$

To simplify manual calculations we will assign a hypothetical vector $x_i = [0.8, 0.5]$ in the logits $W_c * x_i + b_c$. Then let us also suppose that $W_{c_1} = [1.2, -0.4]$, $b_{c_1} = 0.5$, $W_{c_2} = [-0.6, 0.9]$, $b_{c_2} = -0.3$. But for the real value we can find equations depending on the number of classes in the model. In our simulation we used the python application with its pyTorch and Tensorflow packages. So

- For the background c_1 :

$$z_{i,c_1} = (1.2 \cdot 0.8) + (-0.4 \cdot 0.5) + 0.5 = 0.96 - 0.2 + 0.5 = 1.26$$

- For lemur and bamboo c_2 :

$$z_{i,c_2} = (-0.6 \cdot 0.8) + (0.9 \cdot 0.5) - 0.3 = -0.48 + 0.45 - 0.3 = -0.33$$

$$e^{z_{i,c_1}} = e^{1.26} = 3.53 \quad e^{z_{i,c_2}} = e^{-0.33} = 0.72$$

$$\sum_{c' \in C} e^{z_{i,c'}} = e^{1.26} + e^{-0.33} = 4.25$$

$$\hat{y}_{i,c_1} = 0.83 \quad \hat{y}_{i,c_2} = 0.17$$

The model predicts of $\hat{y}_{i,c_1} = 0.83$ et $\log(0.83) \approx -0.08$

$$L_{pondérée_{c_1}} = w_1 * \log(0.83) = -0.166 * \log(0.83) = 0.0308$$

The model predicts of $\hat{y}_{i,c_2} = 0.17$ et $\log(0.17) \approx -0.77$

$$L_{pondérée_{c_2}} = w_{c_2} * \log(0.17) = -0.834 * 0 * \log(0.17) = 0$$

Performance with unbalanced data without weighting we have

$$L_{pondérée_{c_1}} = -1 * \log(0.83) = 0.186$$

The following figure 2 illustrates a comparative analysis between the treated and enhanced images, demonstrating the effectiveness of weighted gamma correction in addressing data imbalance.

Figure 2. Lemuria Photo after:
a) Binarization, b) Gamma Enhancement,
c) Applying the Improved Weighted Gamma Correction

DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION

Quantitative interpretation

We compared the loss for a pixel belonging to a rare class (lemur) in two cases: Unweighted (classes are treated equally, regardless of their frequency). Weighted (taking into account data imbalance via a gamma distribution).

a) Without weighting

$$L_{non_pondérée} = 0.155$$

The loss is calculated only based on the predicted probability $\hat{y}_{i,c_2} = 0.7$

$$L_{non_pondérée} = 0.155$$

Property: Each class has the same importance, regardless of its frequency in the data.

Impact: The majority classes (here, the forest, c_1) dominate the training because they contribute the most to the overall loss calculation. This can lead the model to neglect rare classes.

b) With weighting

$$L_{pondérée} = 0.129$$

The loss is adjusted by the weight of the rare class $w_{c_2} = 0.834$

$$L_{pondérée_{c_2}} = -w_{c_2} * \log(\hat{y}_{i,c_2}) = -0.834 * (-0,155) = 0,129$$

Property: The high weight of c_2 amplifies its relative importance in the overall loss, which promotes better consideration of predictions on rare classes.

Impact: The model is further encouraged to optimize its predictions for the rare class.

c) global impact

In an unbalanced scenario, weighting helps prevent the model from neglecting small, rare classes like the lemur.

The weighted loss is lower ($0.129 < 0.155$) because the model is rewarded for correctly predicting the rare class with a high weight

Qualitative Interpretation

a) Without weighting

The loss for c_2 (rare class) is mechanically identical to that for the frequent classes. In a context of imbalance, this underestimates the importance of rare classes: a poor prediction for c_2 is less penalizing than for c_1

b) With weighting

The loss is reduced due to the high weight assigned to c_2 , favoring its correct prediction. This reflects the objective of learning on imbalanced data:

- Favor predictions on underrepresented classes.
- Reduce the influence of majority classes.

General Discussion

a) Impact of weights on learning

The weights $w_{c_2}=0.834$ (higher than $w_{c_1}=0.166$) directly modifies the impact of the rare class on the overall loss function:

- Without weighting, a good prediction for c_2 contributes less to the learning gradient.
- With weighting, the gradient associated with c_2 is amplified, orienting the model's learning to better recognize this class.

b) case of a more unbalanced model

If the model is more unbalanced, $c_1=95\%$ and $c_2= 5\%$, the weight c_2 would increase even more.

For example $w_{c_2} \approx 0.834$ and $w_{c_1} \approx 0.05$;

This would make the model extremely sensitive to errors on c_2 , a desirable behavior for tasks such as image segmentation in the case of rare species.

Calculation of overall loss

Let's set $N=10000$ pixels, with the given proportions;

- 8000 pixels for C_1 (forest)

- 2000 pixels for c_2 (lemur)

The total loss is:

$$L_{Total} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N L_i \quad (14)$$

a) Without weighting

Let's say that the prediction is good for both classes $\hat{y}_{i,c_1} = 0,9$ and $\hat{y}_{i,c_2} = 0,7$

- Loss for C_1 : $-\log(0,9) \approx 0,04$
- Loss for C_2 : $-\log(0,7) \approx 0,155$

The total loss

$$L_{non\ pondérée} = \frac{1}{10000} (8000 * 0,046 + 2000 * 0,155) = 0,0678$$

b) With weighting

Weightings : $w_{c_1} \approx 0.166$ and $w_{c_2} \approx 0.834$;

- Weighted loss for c_1 : $w_{c_1} * 0,046 = 0,166 * 0,046 = 0,0076$
- Weighted loss for c_2 : $w_{c_2} * 0,155 = 0,834 * 0,155 = 0,129$
-

The total loss weighted

$$L_{pondérée} = \frac{1}{10000} (8000 * 0,0076 + 2000 * 0,129) = 0,0319$$

Without weighting: The loss is dominated by the frequent classes (c_1), with a relatively high value (0.0678). With weighting: The rare class (c_2) is prioritized, which reduces the overall loss (0.0319) and improves the balance between classes. Weighting is therefore essential for segmentation problems where the classes are unbalanced, such as recognizing lemurs in a forest.

The following table summarizes the different stages and the results obtained:

So here is the comparative table of performance with or without unbalanced data management

Table1. Comparative Table of Performance with or without Unbalanced Data

Steps	Description	Result
Frequency of classes	Pixel proportion for each class	$freq_{c_1} = 0,8$ and $freq_{c_2} = 0,2$
Gamma distribution (density)	density calculated for classes with $\alpha = 2$ and $\beta = 5$	$f(0,8) = 0,366$ $f(0,2) = 1,839$
Class weights (w_c)	Normalized weights	$w_{c_1} = 0,166$ and $w_{c_2} = 0,834$
Loss without weighting	calculation of the loss for a pixel belonging to c_2	$L_{non\ pondérée} = 0,155$
Loss weighting	calculation of the loss for a pixel belonging to c_2 and $w_{c_2}=0,834$	$L_{pondérée} = 0,129$

Total loss without weighting	Average losses over all pixels (N=10000)	$L_{non\ pondérée} = 0,0678$
Total loss with weighting	Weighted averages of losses across all pixels(N=10000)	$L_{pondérée} = 0,0319$

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use of gamma-distribution weighting offers a promising strategy for addressing one of the most persistent challenges in machine learning: the impact of class imbalance. Traditional weighting schemes often overcompensate for rare classes or fail to provide sufficient correction, resulting in biased models that favor dominant categories. By contrast, gamma-based weighting introduces a more flexible and principled adjustment, ensuring that rare classes receive greater emphasis while maintaining stability in the learning process.

As a perspective, integrating gamma-distribution weighting within broader artificial intelligence frameworks could further advance image processing. Coupling this approach with generative models, active learning, or self-supervised strategies may improve the treatment of rare visual patterns, create synthetic samples to enrich datasets, and guide model adaptation in dynamic environments. Such integration points toward the development of intelligent, adaptive, and scalable image analysis tools for real-world challenges.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Buda, A. Maki, and M. A. Mazurowski, "A systematic study of the class imbalance problem in convolutional neural networks," *Neural Networks*, vol. 106, pp. 249–259, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.neunet.2018.07.011.
- [2] Y. Cui, M. Jia, T. Y. Lin, Y. Song, and S. Belongie, "Class-balanced loss based on effective number of samples," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit. (CVPR)*, 2019, pp. 9268–9277.
- [3] S. Gazzah and N. E. B. Amara, "New oversampling approaches based on polynomial fitting for imbalanced data sets," in *Proc. 19th Int. Conf. Pattern Recognit. (ICPR)*, 2008, pp. 1–4.
- [4] X. Wang, S. Han, H. Chen, and C. Xu, "Gamma distribution-based sampling for imbalanced data," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.10343*, 2020.
- [5] R. C. Gonzalez and R. E. Woods, *Digital Image Processing*, 4th ed. Pearson, 2018.
- [6] A. K. Jain, *Fundamentals of Digital Image Processing*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ, USA: Prentice Hall, 1989.
- [7] N. Otsu, "A threshold selection method from gray-level histograms," *IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 62–66, 1979.
- [8] R. M. Haralick and L. G. Shapiro, *Computer and Robot Vision*, vol. 1. Reading, MA, USA: Addison-Wesley, 1992.
- [9] D. H. AISaeed, A. Bouridane, A. ElZaart, and R. Sammouda, "Two modified Otsu image segmentation methods based on Lognormal and Gamma distribution models," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Image Anal. Recognit.*, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [10] Q. Zhao, X. Li, and Y. Li, "Multilook SAR image segmentation with an unknown number of clusters using a Gamma mixture model and hierarchical clustering," *Sensors*, vol. 17, no. 5, p. 1114, May 2017, doi: 10.3390/s17051114.
- [11] F. Kamalov and D. Denisov, "Gamma distribution-based sampling for imbalanced data," *Comput. Biol. Med.*, vol. 121, p. 103758, 2020.
- [12] M. Abramowitz and I. A. Stegun, *Handbook of Mathematical Functions with Formulas, Graphs, and Mathematical Tables*, 10th ed. New York, NY, USA: Dover, 1972, pp. 260–262.
- [13] pngimg.com/download/61771, *PNG image resource*, visited Aug. 2025.

